

Genomic Eye Color Classification with Machine Learning

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Introduction

We performed eye color classification with machine learning on 78 tiled genomes from the Personal Genome Project and consistently predicted eye color to **95% accuracy**.

We then located the HERC2 gene and a SNP in the OCA2/HERC2 region responsible for the blue eye color with strong statistical significance.

The Arvados Lightning Project [1] is designed to compact the genomes from their raw (gff, gvcf) format to a new representation allowing for simple and consistent naming, annotation, queries, machine learning, and clinical screening.

Using Lightning, the genomes are tiled—a technique that divides the genome into about 10 million overlapping, variable-length sequences, or “tiles”, each with a unique 24-base tag at each end. This tiling process produces a one dimensional NumPy array of integers representing a specific tile variant at each tile position.

The **Harvard Personal Genome** project curates genomes made public by volunteers as well as survey data. We used the Basic 2015 Phenotypes survey, which contain survey responses for left/right eye color. Survey respondents were asked to classify their own eye color into one of 24 groups (see graphic below) and provide a brief description of their eye color.

Above: the set of 24 images used for classification. Source: Franssen, Luuk, Joris E. Coppens, and Thomas JTP van den Berg. "Grading of iris color with an extended photographic reference set." *Journal of optometry* 1.1 (2008): 36-40.

Materials and Methods

We used the Python library scikit-learn [4], to produce the machine learning algorithm, with a **Linear Support Vector Classifier** and l1 regularization. We used the “left” eye color from survey responses, but there were no significant differences upon using right eye color.

From the eye color chart, groups 1 to 13 were classified as **blue** as they lacked dark pigmentation. From 14 on, the eye colors evidently contained brown pigmentation, so they were classified as **not blue**. There were a total of 78 total respondents who also had tiled genomes, and we used these data with their respective genomes as inputs to our classifier.

Using a grid-search cross validation, we determined the optimal hyperparameters included a C value of .06 and balanced class weight (see “Accuracy vs. C value” graph below).

Above: accuracy versus C value from the grid search cross validation. We used a C-value of .06, but there was no significant difference when choosing values in the same order of magnitude.

We found our classifier had **84.6 ± 9.5%** accuracy using 10-fold cross validation and **88%** accuracy using leave-one-out cross validation.

There were 17/78 participants in total who described their eye color as “hazel” in the survey and the classifier consistently misclassified 6 of them; we performed a categorical exclusion of all participants who responded with hazel and reran our classifier.

After the hazel exclusion, the classifier achieved **94.6 ± 8.4%** accuracy via 10-fold cross validation and **95%** accuracy by leave-one-out cross validation.

Results

Training and prediction took approximately two minutes in total. Originally, classifier found ~45 coefficients, and the highest weighted tile was index **1792420** in the array with weight 0.85 (see “Coefficient Weights” graph). With the categorical hazel exclusion, the classifier found just two coefficients, and same tile had the highest weight of 0.93.

We found that the tile at index 1792420 was located on chromosome 15 from base pairs **28,365,579 to 28,365,804**. This is consistent with base pairs of the **HERC2** gene, which codes for eye color [2]. The NCBI gene database specifies that HERC2 is located at 15q13.1, from base pairs **28,356,183 to 28,567,313**.

We saw one consistent difference upon inspecting the tile variants, an **A>G SNP** on the 61st index. This SNP corresponded with **rs12913832**, a known SNP in the OCA2/HERC2 region [2]. We mapped this SNP with survey responses and performed a Fisher exact test on the results. Whether or not hazel was excluded, the results were statistically significant at $p < .0001$.

Above: coefficient weights on a logarithmic scale, in descending order. The highest coefficients is at index 1792420, with a weight close to 1..

Left: confusion matrix from leave-one-out cross validation with categorical exclusion of hazel.

Right: confusion matrix from leave-one-out validation with all data

Above: table used for the Fisher Exact test with categorical hazel exclusion; we did not include the A>A SNP because there were not enough samples. We found $p=9.49 * 10^{13}$

Conclusion

The Personal Genome Project’s public genomic data and the Arvados Lightning project allows complex applications such as machine learning to be run in a significantly shorter time than raw processing. Using tiled genomes and machine learning, we located the HERC2 gene and a specific SNP in the HERC2 region that determines eye color.

All scripts used are open-source and on GitHub in the form of Jupyter Notebooks [4]. A docker image is optionally provided for easy reuse, and an Arvados pipeline is available at <https://curover.se/su92l-j7dog-y6owdqvhkhkbizy> so this analysis can be rerun and results can be easily reproduced.

References

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